

3D Printing of Continuous Sized Carbon Fiber Reinforced PA6 Composites

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3D printing of continuous fiber reinforced composites (CFRTP-FDM)

- 3D printing of continuous fiber reinforced composites (CFRTP-FDM) have the advantages of simple forming process, low cost and mold-less, and capability to produce complex structure, but mechanical properties are caused by poor interfacial performance with the use of dry fiber as the reinforcement.

Schematic of CFRTP-FDM

Advantages: Simple process, low cost and complex structure

Disadvantages : low mechanical properties and poor interfacial performance

Sizing treatment process for CFRTP-FDM

- To promote the interfacial performance, a solution infiltration process is performed to pre-treat carbon fiber and obtain new sized carbon fiber (SCF), and SCF are used to print composites.
- Sizing agent: PA845H, water-based polyamide solids dispersion
- Reinforcement: virgin carbon fiber(VCF), sized carbon fiber(SCF)
- Matrix: PA6

Schematic illustration of sizing treatment for CFRTP-FDM

Surface compositions and mechanical properties of VCF and SCF

- Mechanical properties of SCF/PA6 are dramatically improved compared with VCF/PA6 composites.

Interface microstructures and fracture patterns of VCF and SCF

● VCF/PA6

● SCF/PA6

- For SCF/PA6, poor interfacial performance is recognized, fiber bundle is only surrounded by PA6 matrix and there is no obvious penetration with just few fibers outside the tow being impregnated and most of fibers being loosely packaged, as seen in Fig. a and b;
- For SCF/PA6, full impregnation is achieved and residual resin is observed on the pull-out fiber surface (Fig. d and e) indicating that sizing treatment can not only improve the infiltration of resin into fiber bundle but also enhance the bonding strength between them, causing the improvement of interfacial performance finally.
- When composite breaks, large fibers pull-out and layers delamination are happen in VCF/PA6 (Fig. c), while not observed in SCF/PA6 (Fig. f) leading to improved mechanical properties.